

Awareness about Invisalign among Dental Students- Cross Sectional Study

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Abstract:-

Object: To assess the awareness about Invisalign among dental students of first year, second year, third year, final year and interns of Pushpagiri College of Dental Science.

Materials and Method: A cross sectional questionnaire study conducted among Dental Students of Pushpagiri College of Dental Sciences, by collecting data using questionnaire. Students of first year, second year, third year ,final year and interns were included for the study . A questionnaire composed of 10 questions, designed to assess awareness about Invisalign among students .Fifty students participated in the study.

Result: The study reveals that out of fifty attendees – I)83.3% attendees didn't used invisalign before II)91.7% of attendees aware about Invisalign III)83.3% attendees knows in which cases Invisalign can be use IV)83.3% attendees knows Invisalign have better oral hygiene than traditional brackets.

Conclusion: Awareness program regarding Invisalign are necessary to create awareness among dental students.

Keywords:- Awareness, Invisalign , dental students.

I. INTRODUCTION

Now a days , not only adults have influence of appearance in their professional and personal lives but also children have influence of the same . The maloccluded patients when think about the correction of their malaligned teeth , the first thing that come to their mind are braces, and wires . However , according to the demands and needs of the patients , dentistry has been revolutionized . Dentists are concerned about the aesthetics and it is the major concerns among patients whotakes orthodontic treatment . To tackle the increasing aesthetic insist for an alternative to conventional braces , researchers have developed several solutions , such as composite braces , ceramic, lingual orthodontics and clear aligners . clear aligners are the new age Aesthetic Orthodontic Treatment . The demand of Invisalign is increasing nowadays due to its esthetic demand for those patients who are indisposed of wearing usual orthodontic appliances . Invisalign are thin transparent removable unobserved plastic aligners for successful moving of teeth into their required position . The patient is instructed to wear such aligner for approximately 20 hours per day and is supposed to change approximately every two weeks . Each aligner will shift the teeth around 0.25 to 0.3 mm . In current years , the figure of teenager patients

looking for orthodontic treatment has increased , so the aesthetics of the orthodontic appliance has become a topic of interest . The orthodontic patient today demands a beautiful smile at the end of treatment , but is equally concerned with appearance during the treatment . Due to increasing esthetic demands of adolescent patients and clinical simplification in customizing lingual appliances , the indication of lingual orthodontics today is extended to adolescents apart from young patients .

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The awareness about Invisalign questionnaire consisting of 10 questions . Practice were administered to a sample of 50 dental students of first year, second year, third year , final year and interns in Pushpagiri College Of Dental Sciences, Thiruvalla.

III. QUESTIONNAIRE

- A. Are you aware about Invisalign
 - Yes
 - No
- B. Did you ever use Invisalign ?
 - Yes
 - No
- C. In which age group Invisalign can be use ?
 - Below 30 years
 - Above 30 years
 - Below 50 years
- D. Do you think Invisalign is expensive ?
 - Yes
 - No
- E. In which cases Invisalign can be use ?
 - Mild crowded teeth
 - Spacing Problem(1-5mm)
 - Proclination
 - All of the above
- F. How long an invisalign should wear a day?
 - 6hrs
 - 22hrs
 - 14hrs
 - During night

G. Do you think Invisalign have better oral hygiene than traditional brackets?

- Yes
- No

H. Is Invisalign applicable in premolar extraction cases?

- Yes
- No

I. Do you think dental appointments need more for Invisalign than traditional brackets?

- Yes
- No

J. How frequently Invisalign must be changed?

- Two weeks
- One month
- Two months
- Six months

IV. RESULT

Fig. 1: Are you aware about invisalign?

Fig. 2: Did you ever use invisalign?

Fig. 3: In which age group invisalign can be use?

Fig. 4: In which cases invisalign can be use?

Fig. 5: How long an invisalign should wear?

Fig. 6: Do you think invisalign is expensive?

Fig. 7: Do you think Invisalign have better oral hygiene than traditional brackets?

Fig. 8: Is Invisalign applicable in premolar extraction cases?

Fig. 9: Do you think dental appointments need more for Invisalign than traditional brackets?

Fig. 10: How frequently Invisalign must be changed?

V. DISCUSSION

The study was conducted based on a self prepared questionnaire circulated among 50 students of Pushpagiri college of Dental Sciences, Thiruvalla , via Google Forms . There are 10 direct questions focused on the awareness about Invisalign among dental students and interns on the awareness about Invisalign . Majority of the participants belonged to the age of 18-25 years .

In a developing nation like our country India , where there are numerous dental colleges, an attempt was made to know the awareness level of the dental students and interns about the Invisalign . High level of education may be one of the main reasons that majority of our sample population had medium-high level of awareness . The level of awareness of this sample population is reflective of the quality of

education provided and the clinical exposure they receive in the dental college . The limitation in this study is that it was conducted only on dental students and interns in one college and was not representative of dental students of all over the country and hence the results can not be generalized . Other weakness in the study is that it has a small sample size of 50 individuals . This study highlights the significant role that the dental college plays in the level of awareness about Invisalign among dental students and thus upcoming dentists . This in turn ensures that these dentists can then provide the best quality of treatment to their patients.

As per the survey conducted , about 91.7% of the participants would like to increase their awareness in the field of orthodontics . The necessary arrangements for this can be made by conducting lectures which are more clinically relevant in classes and by providing opportunities

to the students to attend more CDE (continuing dental education) programmes held by leading orthodontists.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, awareness about Invisalign was fair among the study participants. Inadequate knowledge significantly affects the quality of treatment that they can provide to their patients. This study explored the awareness level of the dental students and interns about the Invisalign . This helped in assessing the effectiveness of the existent dental curriculum and understanding the changes to be made to improve the general awareness and knowledge of upcoming dentists.

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